

Assessment of *Bacillus Cereus* Isolated from Petrochemical Waste (Bitumen) for Electricity Generation Using Microbial Fuel Cell Technology

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Abstract

The growing environmental concerns associated with petrochemical waste pollution necessitate sustainable remediation strategies. This study aims to evaluate the bioremediation capabilities of *Bacillus cereus* in degrading petrochemical pollutants and its potential for generating bioelectricity using Microbial Fuel Cells (MFCs). Water and soil samples contaminated with petrochemical wastes were collected from Agbabu, Ondo State, Nigeria. *Bacillus cereus* was isolated and characterized using cultural techniques. Bioelectricity generation of *Bacillus cereus* was conducted using Microbial Fuel Cell (MFCs) technique. Physicochemical analyses were performed using standard methods. *Bacillus cereus* is a Gram-positive, rod-shaped, catalase negative, and nitrate-reducing bacterium. It appeared as white, round and irregular/rhizoids on the plates. Heavy metal concentrations were higher in water compared to soil samples. In the microbial fuel cells, the chamber with KMnO₄ demonstrated higher bioelectricity generation, with voltage outputs ranging from 0.524V to 1.058V and current up to 0.44A. Physicochemical content revealed soil pH of 6.73 and water pH of 8.3, with notable differences in conductivity and total dissolved solids. The study shows that *Bacillus cereus* exhibits robust potential for bioremediation of petrochemical pollutants while simultaneously generating bioelectricity. The significant reductions in TPAH levels for both soil and water samples further support the efficacy of this approach.

Keywords: Electricity, Microbial Fuel Cell (MFC), Petrochemical waste, Current, Voltage

INTRODUCTION

The widespread use of petrochemicals has led to serious environmental pollution from persistent and toxic wastes. These pollutants, primarily hydrocarbons and heavy metals, accumulate in soil and water, causing ecological imbalance and posing health risks to humans and aquatic life (Wu *et al.*, 2023). Addressing this challenge requires sustainable and eco-friendly clean-up strategies that are both effective and economically viable. One promising solution lies in microbial bioremediation, which utilizes the metabolic capacity of microorganisms to degrade pollutants into less harmful forms. Among these microorganisms, *Bacillus cereus* has drawn attention due to its

resilience, adaptability, and proven ability to degrade complex hydrocarbons (Ijah and Antai, 2003). The bacterium's robust enzymatic system and spore-forming ability enable it to thrive in harsh petrochemical environments, making it a potential candidate for efficient remediation of bitumen and other hydrocarbon wastes. Beyond remediation, recent advances in microbial fuel cell (MFC) technology have provided an innovative platform for coupling biodegradation with bioenergy recovery. MFCs exploit the metabolic activity of microorganisms to convert chemical energy stored in organic substrates directly into electrical energy (Logan *et al.*, 2006). This dual function—waste degradation and energy generation—offers a sustainable and circular approach to managing petrochemical pollution while addressing the global energy crisis. Despite growing interest in this field, limited studies have examined the dual potential of *Bacillus cereus* in both hydrocarbon degradation and electricity generation from bitumen-contaminated sites. Understanding this potential is vital for designing sustainable biotechnological systems for pollution control and renewable energy generation. Hence, this study was designed to investigate the ability of *Bacillus cereus* isolated from petrochemical waste (bitumen) to degrade hydrocarbons and generate electricity in a microbial fuel cell system.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Study area

This study was conducted in Agbabu, Ondo State, Nigeria, is an area rich in bitumen. Soil and surface water samples were collected from three designated sites within the village using sterile equipment, with additional control samples from uncontaminated areas. The sample was collected into clean bottle, the samples were well labelled and transported aseptically to the Bioenergy Research Laboratory, Microbiology department, Federal University of Technology, Akure. Samples were stored at 4°C and processed within 24 hours.

Physicochemical analysis

Physicochemical parameters including pH, electrical conductivity (EC), Total organic matter concentrations of ammonia, calcium, magnesium, sodium, potassium, total nitrogen, copper, zinc were determined using Hanna Instrument for pH, COD, BOD, TSS, turbidity, FOG, and salinity. EC, Atomic Absorption Spectrophotometer (AAS) Buck Scientific 210 VGP for the mineral composition and Conductivity Measuring Bridge (CDM210) for EC.

Isolation of Microorganism

Isolation of the microorganisms were carried out according to the method described by Fawole and Oso (2012). One gram of the bitumen was measured using a weighing balance and a sterile foil paper into a test tube. Ten folds serial dilution of the sample was carried out using sterile distilled water. One millilitre aliquot of the diluted sample (10^3 and 10^6) was plated out using the pour plate technique into Petri dishes with 20 ml of molten culture media Mannitol-Egg Yolk-Polymyxin agar. The culture media were covered and incubated in an inverted position at 37 °C for 24 hours for the bacteria in triplicate before examination for microbial growth. The bacterial isolates were purified by streaking on fresh sterile nutrient agar before sub culturing. The pure isolates were temporarily stored on slants and kept at 4°C for further use. Colony counts were carried out on plates in triplicate.

Identification of Microorganism

Identification of the pure bacteria was determined using cultural and morphological features. Bacteria isolates were further identified using biochemical tests according to (Cheesbrough, 2006).

Microbial Fuel Cell Construction

MFC Fabrication

The MFC were constructed in modification to the description of Adegunloye and Olotu (2017). The anode and cathode chambers were fabricated using screw-capped plastic containers with drilled holes on one side of each container ensuring that the holes were exactly opposite each other. The total working volume of 1200 ml was contained in both chambers. Salt bridge (proton exchange membrane) contained in 15 cm length and 3.81 cm diameter PVC pipes were fixed into the holes of the two containers with the aid of epoxy adhesive to avoid leakage. Holes of two millimetres (mm) in diameter were drilled on top of each plastic containers lids as wire point inputs. This set-up was filled with water past the holes/joints and allowed to stay overnight to check for possible leakages.

Bioremediation

The bitumen was dissolved in dichloromethane and mixed with soil or water samples in conical flasks, with nutrient broth added. Treatments included controls and *Bacillus cereus* inoculation. Flasks were incubated on a shaker at 30°C for 14 days, with samples taken every 5 days for pH, bacterial count, and hydrocarbon analysis.

Data were statistically analyzed using ANOVA and Duncan's test in SPSS (v22.0), with significance set at $P \leq 0.05$.

RESULTS

Table 1: Biochemical and Identity of *Bacillus cereus*

Characteristics	Result
Catalase	+
Citrate	+
Gram Staining	+
Growth in KCN	+
Indole	+
Motility	+
Oxidase	-
Shape	Rod
Spore	+
VP (VogesProskauer)	+
MR (Methyl Red)	-
Sugar Fermentation of	
Arabinose	-
Galactose	-
Glucose	+
Lactose	-
Maltose	+
Mannitol	-
Raffinose	-
Sucrose	+

Keys: + = positive, - = negative

The results showed that *Bacillus cereus* is a Gram-positive, catalase-positive, oxidase-negative rod-shaped bacterium capable of forming spores. It demonstrated positive for citrate utilization, growth in KCN, indole production, and the Voges-Proskauer test, while testing negative for the Methyl Red test. Sugar fermentation revealed that the isolate could ferment glucose, maltose, and sucrose, but not arabinose, galactose, lactose, mannitol, or raffinose. These biochemical characteristics are consistent with the typical profile of *Bacillus cereus*.

Table 2: Molecular Identity of *Bacillus cereus*

Isolate code	Molecular Identity	Accession Number
A	<i>Bacillus cereus</i>	PP107870.1

The molecular identification of the bacterial isolate has an accession number of PP107870. The DNA sequence of the generated confirms the bacteria isolate as *Bacillus cereus*. This genetic data provides additional confirmation of the organism's identity and can be used for further genetic comparisons with other *B. cereus* strains.

Physicochemical Characteristics of Soil and Water Samples

The physicochemical content of soil and water samples revealed distinct characteristics. The soil sample had a pH of 6.73, conductivity of 48 μ S/cm, and total dissolved solids of 550 mg/L. The water sample showed a pH of 8.3, conductivity of 33 μ S/cm, and total dissolved solids of 960 mg/L. Other parameters such as chloride, sulphate, phosphate, ammonia, nitrate, BOD, COD, and organic matter content were also measured and compared between the two samples.

Table 3: Physicochemical Characteristics of Soil and Water Samples

Parameter	Samples	
	Soil	Water
pH	6.73	8.3
Conductivity (μ S/cm)	48	33
Total dissolved solid	550	960
Turbidity (NTU)	Nil	13
Suspended solid (mg/L)	Nil	0.07
Chloride (mg/L)	72.89(mg/Kg)	10.93(mg/L)
Sulphate	3.78(mg/Kg)	4.66(mg/L)
Phosphate (mg/L)	NIL	4.54
Ammonia	27.45 mg/kg	16.12 mg/kg
Phosphorus (mg/Kg)	12.07	NIL
Nitrate	68.69 (mg/Kg)	13.35(mg/L)
Nitrite	2.1	0.8 mg/L
BOD (mg/L)	19	4.65
COD (mg/L)	670	380
Oil and grease (mg/L)	NIL	0.002
Nitrogen (mg/Kg)	0.06	NIL
Total organic carbon (%)	0.12	13

Microbial Fuel Cell (MFC) Performance

Chamber A (H₂O as electron acceptor)

Current: Varied across the day, averaging ~0.02A in the morning, dipping in the afternoon (0.00–0.01A), and rising slightly in the evening (up to 0.02A, with one outlier at 0.20A). **Voltage:** More stable than current; ranged from 0.149V to 0.886V, with generally lower readings in the afternoon and higher in the evening.

Days	Current (A)	Current (A)	Current (A)	Voltage (V)	Voltage (V)	Voltage (V)
	Morning	Afternoon	Evening	Morning	Afternoon	Evening
1	0.01 ± 0.00 ^a	0.01 ± 0.00 ^a	0.02 ± 0.00 ^a	0.29 ± 0.02 ^b	0.12 ± 0.01 ^c	0.20 ± 0.02 ^c
2	0.03 ± 0.00 ^a	0.01 ± 0.00 ^a	0.01 ± 0.00 ^a	0.52 ± 0.03 ^a	0.21 ± 0.01 ^b	0.19 ± 0.02 ^c
3	0.01 ± 0.00 ^a	0.00 ± 0.00 ^a	0.01 ± 0.00 ^a	0.55 ± 0.03 ^a	0.22 ± 0.02 ^b	0.24 ± 0.02 ^b
4	0.06 ± 0.01 ^a	0.00 ± 0.00 ^a	0.01 ± 0.00 ^a	0.80 ± 0.04 ^a	0.25 ± 0.02 ^b	0.27 ± 0.03 ^b
5	0.00 ± 0.00 ^b	0.01 ± 0.00 ^a	0.01 ± 0.00 ^a	0.14 ± 0.01 ^c	0.26 ± 0.02 ^b	0.10 ± 0.01 ^d
6	0.00 ± 0.00 ^b	0.00 ± 0.00 ^a	0.00 ± 0.00 ^a	0.25 ± 0.02 ^c	0.22 ± 0.02 ^b	0.26 ± 0.02 ^b
7	0.00 ± 0.00 ^b	0.00 ± 0.00 ^a	0.00 ± 0.00 ^a	0.24 ± 0.02 ^c	0.20 ± 0.01 ^c	0.27 ± 0.02 ^b

Values are presented as *mean ± standard deviation* (n = 3). Means with different superscript letters within the same column differ significantly at $P \leq 0.05$

Chamber B (KMnO₄ as electron acceptor)

Days	Current (A)	Current (A)	Current (A)	Voltage (V)	Voltage (V)	Voltage (V)
	Morning	Afternoon	Evening	Morning	Afternoon	Evening
1	0.35 ± 0.02 ^a	0.05 ± 0.01 ^c	0.10 ± 0.01 ^b	0.90 ± 0.05 ^a	0.88 ± 0.04 ^a	0.85 ± 0.03 ^a
2	0.12 ± 0.01 ^d	0.25 ± 0.02 ^b	0.20 ± 0.02 ^b	0.52 ± 0.04 ^c	0.85 ± 0.03 ^a	0.88 ± 0.05 ^a
3	0.40 ± 0.03 ^a	0.10 ± 0.01 ^c	0.27 ± 0.02 ^b	1.05 ± 0.06 ^a	0.50 ± 0.04 ^c	0.85 ± 0.03 ^a
4	0.05 ± 0.00 ^d	0.02 ± 0.00 ^d	0.04 ± 0.00 ^c	0.80 ± 0.03 ^b	0.55 ± 0.04 ^b	0.60 ± 0.03 ^b
5	0.12 ± 0.01 ^d	0.10 ± 0.01 ^c	0.37 ± 0.02 ^a	0.83 ± 0.04 ^b	0.84 ± 0.03 ^a	0.90 ± 0.04 ^a
6	0.10 ± 0.01 ^d	0.40 ± 0.02 ^a	0.45 ± 0.02 ^a	0.85 ± 0.05 ^b	1.00 ± 0.04 ^a	1.05 ± 0.05 ^a
7	0.07 ± 0.00 ^d	0.25 ± 0.02 ^b	0.30 ± 0.02 ^a	0.65 ± 0.03 ^c	1.10 ± 0.05 ^a	1.08 ± 0.04 ^a

Values are presented as *mean ± standard deviation* (n = 3). Means with different superscript letters within the same column differ significantly at $P \leq 0.05$

Chamber B demonstrated significantly higher current output compared to Chamber A. Morning current readings ranged from 0.05A to 0.42A, with most values above 0.09A. Afternoon readings showed greater variability, ranging from 0.01A to 0.41A. Evening current measurements were the highest, ranging from 0.10A to 0.44A.

Voltage output in Chamber Two was consistently higher than in Chamber One. Morning voltages ranged from 0.524V to 1.058V, with most readings above 0.8V. Afternoon voltages showed similar range, from 0.522V to 1.079V. Evening voltage measurements were the highest and most consistent, ranging from 0.786V to 1.055V

DISCUSSION

The isolation and identification of *Bacillus cereus* confirmed known biochemical and morphological traits, supported by molecular identification (Accession: PP107870.1). Environmental analysis showed microbial diversity and signs of anthropogenic contamination, including elevated nitrate levels (Rousk *et al.*, 2009). Heavy metals were found in both soil and water, with water samples showing higher concentrations (Ayangbenro and Babalola, 2017). Electricity generation was significantly better with KMnO_4 (Chamber B), suggesting optimization potential for bioelectric applications. Observed broth reduction in Chamber A implied active microbial metabolism, supporting the dual functionality of *B. cereus* in energy generation and bioremediation. These findings align with studies by Logan *et al.* (2006), who demonstrated the potential of various bacterial species in microbial fuel cells for sustainable energy production. The marked difference in voltage and current generation between chambers using KMnO_4 and H_2O as electron acceptors can be attributed to their distinct redox potentials and electron transfer capacities. Potassium permanganate (KMnO_4) possesses a higher oxidative potential ($E^\circ = +1.695$ V) than molecular oxygen ($E^\circ = +1.229$ V), making it a more efficient terminal electron acceptor. This enhanced redox capability facilitates faster electron flow from the anode to the cathode, thereby improving current density and voltage output. Additionally, KMnO_4 's strong oxidizing nature supports greater oxygen availability in the cathode chamber, reducing internal resistance and enhancing proton transfer across the salt bridge. These combined effects contribute to the observed higher and more stable voltage (0.524 – 1.058 V) and current (up to 0.44 A) in Chamber B compared to the H_2O chamber, which exhibited lower and fluctuating readings. Similar findings have been reported by Logan and Regan (2006) and Ayangbenro and Babalola (2017), who noted that electron acceptors with higher redox potentials significantly enhance microbial fuel cell performance by improving electron kinetics and reducing cathodic over potential.

CONCLUSION

This study demonstrates the potential of *B. cereus* in converting hydrocarbon waste into electrical energy through MFC technology, while also offering effective bioremediation of contaminated environments. It underscores the importance of microbial ecology in environmental management and sustainable energy development.

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